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Research Article

**SUADI NURSES' PERCEPTION OF DISASTER MANAGEMENT
IN PANDEMICS AND MASS CASUALTY EVENTS****Hassan Salem Sahlooly**

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Nursing Department - Taif Universityabosalem34@hotmail.com**Abstract:**

The main aims and objectives of the research are reflected in the introduction of this research proposal. It is of the utmost importance to be ready to deal with any emerging or sudden mass casualty or pandemic. The role of nurses is vitally important; therefore, this research will address (in depth) a variety of issues surrounding nurses in the KSA in cases of pandemic or mass casualty. Therefore, one of the most important aims of this research is to improve the readiness of nurses in cases of mass casualty or pandemic.

This research will ethically collect the data in order to unfold the real situation and perception of nurses in cases of mass casualty or pandemic. In addition to the data from the participants the research will use a wide range of literature and theories about the topic. Due to the Covid-19 crises and restrictions, an online questionnaire will be made available for participants to freely respond to the questions. Once the data is correctly and ethically collected, it will be analysed, examined, and evaluated in order to consolidate results and outcomes.

The resources and budget needed to implement this research are reflected in detail under the heading "Resources Required", however, no major resources are needed except the commitment and the engagement with project from the very beginning stage until the completion of the project. In addition, once the research has obtained the full approval and review of the university then it will be published in a scientific journal related to nursing.

Keywords: Nurse, Pandemic, Perception, Management, Mass Casualty.

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INTRODUCTION:

The introduction will include the aims and the objectives of this research proposal in order to give full picture regarding the Saudi nurses' perception of disaster management in pandemics and cases of mass casualty.

Aims

Since the aims of a research are what the research project intends to achieve as long term outcomes (Bryman, 2008), the main aims of this research proposal are:

1. To improve the readiness of the Saudi nurses in case of mass casualty or major health crises as a consequence of health pandemics, such as Covid-19.
2. To create a clear action plan strategy to be implemented in cases of mass casualty or sudden disaster.
3. To offer an on-going training strategy for all nurses in the KSA about what to be done and how to react in cases of mass casualty or Disease outbreaks
4. To consolidate and increase the relationship between nurses and other governmental institutions, such as the Civil Defence Saudi Arabia in the case of major incidents, disasters, or health crises.

Objectives

The main objectives of this research proposal are:

1. To examine and evaluate the Saudi nurses' perception and management in a case of mass disaster or major health pandemic, such as Covid-19.
2. To explore the grade of readiness of nurses in the KSA regarding the Covid-19 pandemic.
3. To investigate and evaluate the available human and non-human resources to tackle disease outbreaks or big natural disasters, such as major earthquake or flooding.

Problem Statement

The Covid-19 crises has unfolded the importance of the readiness of the nurses in KSA when facing a great number of patients in a short period of time. The familiarity with, and the perception of, nurses regarding mass casualty and pandemics must be analysed and investigated in order to enhance the productivity of nurses and meanwhile to increase and improve the coordination between the different sectors and the organisation of society in order to do the right things to reduce the side-effects of any pandemic or mass casualty event.

Therefore, this research proposal is vitally important since the level of risk about Covid-19 is still very high.

This is a problem that needs solution, this research will address this problem with one of the main agents, specifically, nurses. The perception and the readiness of all nurses must be positive and ready to deal with any unexpected pandemic or mass casualty event. The outcomes from the data of this research will be deeply analysed and examined in order to come up with clear conclusion and recommendations to help and support nurses before and during pandemics or mass casualty events.

Background

The sudden emergence of Covid-19 generates a great deal of confusion and unfolded the weaknesses of the whole health systems even in the very rich and advanced countries (WHO, 2021), therefore, the World Health Organisation (WHO, 2021) called for reflection and re-consideration of the complete health system in each country. This research addresses an important sector of any health system which is the nurses. Therefore, this research will give support to the nurses in the KSA and globally and the research will also ease and facilitate the perception of nurses of pandemics and or mass casualty events.

According to the WHO (2021) global cooperation is needed in order to fight Covid-19 and there is an additional need of cooperation among the health workers and staff. A pandemic such as Covid-19 has no borders or limits of spreading, therefore, medical staff and especially frontline workers, such as nurses must be better prepared in order to manage the crisis with full confidence and with better knowledge and tools.

Significance of the Research

The outcomes and the findings of this research will necessarily contribute to new knowledge regarding the readiness of nurses in cases of mass casualty or pandemics. Through scientific research, improvement and progress can be made, and in this case the recommendations of the research will be published in order to benefit a wider range of people, professionals, and local authorities. The outcomes of this research are expected to be viable and reliable, since the collection of the data will be ethically accepted, because previous approval regarding the data collection will be obtained before the collection of the data will start. In addition, the whole process of the research will be under the regulation of supervisors designated by the university.

Research Design

The research design will chronologically and logically link all parts of the research in order to receive solid and reliable outcomes. The measure of the perception

and the management of nurses regarding mass casualty events or pandemics must be the main issue throughout the whole research. The sample, the methodology, and the data collection will be carefully analysed, examined, and evaluated in order to consolidate results and outcomes. The research also will examine and unfold any gap that must be filled in a case of mass casualty or pandemic.

Sample

The scope and scale of the research and the number of nurses in the KSA will be considered when the size of the sample is determined, since there is a correlation between the size of the sample and the total number of nurses in the KSA, because the research will take place in the KSA. Bryman (2008) stated that:

“The term ‘non-probability sampling’ is essentially an umbrella term to capture all forms of sampling” (Bryman, 2008, p. 183).

Therefore, this research will use non-probability sampling in order to cover a good number of participants in a reasonable lapse of time with the minimum financial and economic costs. However, the number of participants expected to respond to the questionnaire will be between 250 to 350 due to the online accessibility and availability offered by internet technology, since the questionnaire will be answered online (anywhere and anytime) (Harding, 2013). There is a high level of expectation regarding the engagement and participation of the nurses of this country in this research, since the motivation and the good behaviour of the nurses will encourage them to participate actively.

METHODOLOGY AND DATA COLLECTION:

This research will use an online questionnaire for the collection of quantitative data. However, the design of the research methodology is cross-sectional design. Bryman (2008) stated that:

“The cross-sectional design is often called a survey design, but the idea of the survey is so closely connected in most people’s mind with questionnaires and structured interviewing that the more generic-sounding term cross-sectional design preferable” (Bryman, 2008, p. 44).

Covid-19 restrictions consolidate the use of an online questionnaire in order to avoid any type of physical contact and to obtain the needed data according to the rules and without breaking the rules and regulations imposed by the KSA government.

According to Holliday (2016):

“Qualitative research will always involve quantitative elements and vice versa” (Holliday, 2016, p. 2).

The above statement consolidates the concept regarding the relationship between qualitative research and quantitative research, although quantitative research is about figures and numbers and qualitative research is regarding opinion, notion, feeling and thoughts, both are interrelated (Holliday, 2016).

The questions of the questionnaire will **NOT** include any **Closed-Ended-Questions** or **Leading Questions** in order to give the participants a good margin of freedom to express themselves (Kvale, 1996).

Procedures

The procedure regarding the data collection will **NOT** take place without a full ethical approval. Once this research proposal and the questions of the questionnaire are submitted and the ethical approval is obtained, then the questionnaire will be put online for the participants via an internet link. When a good number of responses are obtained, then the outcomes of the data will be collected, displayed, and critically analysed and evaluated. It is clear that the participants have the right to be informed regarding the outcomes of the research. The procedure will follow the timeline (Gantt Chart) of the research which is reflected below. The permission to be obtained in order to carry out this research project will be limited to the geographic area of the capital of the KSA – Riyadh, therefore the data will be collected from nurses only from Riyadh.

Data Analysis

Once the data is ethically collected, then it will be condensed, displayed, and conclusions will be drawn. There is a need for the display of the data to be critically and rigorously evaluated and analysed (Miles, Huberman, & Saldaña, 2009). SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) Software will be used to generate charts, tabulated reports, and diagrams. The use of SPSS is vitally important to consolidate viable results and outcomes (Leech, Barrett, & Morgan, 2008).

Ethical Considerations and Review

The anonymity of research participants will be fully respected and granted. Therefore, no personal details will be collected, such as addresses, IP addresses, mobile numbers, or any other personal information. In addition, the participants will have the right not to answer part of, or all of, the questions and to withdraw at any stage of the research. In addition, before putting

the questionnaire online full approval will be obtained from the university, since this research proposal is in alignment with university ethical regulations.

Dissemination of Research Finding

Once the findings of this research are discussed and consolidated by the data analysis outcomes, then the research can be published in a well-known scientific

journal related to the nursing sector. This research will be available for future researchers (public domain) and meanwhile will benefits the students of nursing. Since this research will be rigorous, original, and unique, the research will further develop existing knowledge regarding the topic or will create new knowledge.

Timeline (Gantt Chart)

Activities	Months 2020/2021							
	Sep.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.	Jan.	Feb.	March	April
Introduction								
Literature Review								
Research Design								
Data Collection								
Data Analysis								
Discussion								
Conclusion								
Final Review								
Dissemination								

Resources Required

There is a need for physical material resources and meanwhile there is a need for enough time to read, research, investigate, and above all to have full engagement and commitment with the whole project. Regarding the physical materials needed, there are:

- Laptop or desktop with enough hard-disk memory in order to save and manage big data about the research (with strong password due to the protection of the raw and finished data).
- Microsoft Office (including, Word, Excel, and Access), in order to display the data and to create diagrams and charts.
- Reliable 24/7 internet connection.
- Enough budget to buy academic textbooks and other important materials, such as USBs and quality office stationery.

Management of the Project

Hannagan (2005) in his book management concept and practices defined management as:

“The process of planning, organising, leading, and controlling” (Hannagan, 2005, p. 680).

The above statement is in alignment with what will be done to carry out this research project.

The entire project will be managed, controlled, realised, and implemented by the student; however, the student will follow the constructive instructions and feedback given by the university’s supervisor. Since the attendance of lectures and tutorials is a very important source to gain new knowledge and to consolidate existing knowledge, it will form an

important part of the research. The knowledge gained will be reflected on this research project.

REFERENCES:

1. Black, T. R. (1999). *Doing Qualitative Research in the Social Sciences*. London: Sage.
2. Bryman, A. (1988). *Quantity and Quality in Social Research* (Contemporary Social Research Series ed., Vol. 18). (M. Bulmer, Ed.) London: Unwin Hyman.
3. Bryman, A. (2008). *Social Research Methods* (3rd ed.). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
4. Burns, S., & Bulman, C. (Eds.). (2000). *Reflective Practice in Nursing* (2nd ed.). London: Blackwell Science Ltd.
5. Crotty, M. (1998). *The Foundations of Social Research: Meaning and Perspective in the Research Process*. London: Sage.
6. Edgington, M. (1998). *The Nursery Teacher in Action* (2nd ed.). London: Paul Chapman Publishing Ltd.
7. Harding, J. (2013). *Qualitative Data Analysis from Start to Finish*. London: SAGE Publications.
8. Hart, C. (2009). *Doing Literature Review*. London : Sage Publication Ltd.
9. Holliday, A. (2016). *Doing and Writing Qualitative Research* (3rd ed.). London: Sage.
10. Jackson, S. M., & Bennett, P. J. (1988). *Physiology with Anatomy for Nurses*. London: Baolliere Tindall.
11. Kvale, S. (1996). *Interviews*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
12. Lipscomb, M. (2008, January). Mixed method nursing studies: A critical realist critique. *Nursing Philosophy*, 9(1), 32-45.
13. McFerran, T. (Ed.). (1996). *Oxford Dictionary of Nursing* (2nd ed.). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
14. Miles, M. B., Huberman, A. M., & Saldaña, J. (2009). *Qualitative Data Analysis* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oak, Ca: Sage.
15. Petrie, A., & Sabin, C. (2006). *Medical Statistics at a Glance* (2nd ed.). Blackwell Publishing Ltd: Oxford.
16. Rue, L. W., & Holland, P. G. (1989). *Strategic Management*. McGraw-Hill Book Co., USA: New York.
17. Saudi Ministry of Health. (2021). *Saudi Ministry of Health*. Retrieved February 15, 2021, from Saudi Ministry of Health: <https://www.moh.gov.sa/en/Pages/default.aspx>
18. Silverman, D. (2000). *Doing Qualitative Research*. London: Sage Publications Ltd.
19. Wand, T., White, K., & Patching, J. (2010, September). Applying a realist(ic) framework to the evaluation of a new model of emergency department based mental health nursing practice. *Nursing Inquiry*, 17(3), 233-239.
20. WHO. (2021). *World Health Organization*. Retrieved February 2021, 2021, from WHO Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) Dashboard: https://Covid19.who.int/?gclid=CjwKCAiAmrOBBhA0EiwArn3mfCGZr3fobCOQTuA5XFa9R9RKYVduMVcRKowwV1wiN79gJKNSkBE1yBoC0F8QAvD_BwE
21. Zhang, X. (2010). Discourse analysis of 'China Daily's' Disaster News Reports: An Appraisal Approach. *Unpublished Master's thesis*. Chengdu, China: Chengdu University of Electronic Science and Technology.

Appendix I WHO Data Regarding Covid-19 in KSA

Saudi Arabia Situation

373,368
confirmed cases

6,441
deaths

Source: World Health Organization

Source: (WHO, 2021, p. np)